

EPIDEMIOLOGY OF VAGINAL BIRTHS AMONG HAITIAN AND DOMINICAN PATIENTS IN A HOSPITAL IN THE DOMINICAN REPUBLIC

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Introduction:

We conducted a study using a comprehensive database created from patient records at a hospital in the Dominican Republic to document vaginal births among Haitian and Dominican patients. This database was previously used in another study addressing a different research question.

Methodology:

We conducted a one-month observational study documenting patients undergoing vaginal delivery to identify epidemiological trends and differences between ethnic groups (Haitians/Dominicans). Patients were grouped by age: adolescents (under 19 years of age), adults (29-35), and older women (over 35 years of age).

RESULTS AND COMPARISON:

Out of 162 patients, 68 were Haitian, and 94 were Dominican. The average age of the Haitian women was 26 years old, and the average baby weight was 3,046 grams. The average age for Dominican women was 24 years old, and the average birth weight was 2,979 grams.

Dominican women:

- Under 19 years: 20 patients (21.3%)
- 19-35 years: 62 patients (66.0%)
- Over 35 years: 12 patients (12.8%)

Haitian women:

- Under 19 years: 5 patients (7.35%)
- 19-35 years: 53 patients (77.9%)
- Over 35 years: 3 patients (4.4%)

Comparison with Existing Data:

According to recent surveys, 41% of births in the Dominican Republic and 27% in Haiti are from women under 19 years old (3). In our study, the percentages are lower:

- **Dominican Republic:**
21.3% of births to women under 19 years old.
- **Haiti:**
7.35% of births to women under 19 years old.

Figure 1. Dominican group pie chart (% by age)

Figura 2. Haitian group pie chart (% by age)

REFERENCES

CONCLUSION:

Our study shows fewer adolescent births than previous surveys in the Dominican Republic and Haiti. These discrepancies could be due to differences in sample size, regional healthcare practices, or evolving social trends (5). Although our study offers insight into recent birth trends in 2024, the limited sample size suggests more extensive and updated epidemiological studies. Such research could confirm whether teen birth rates are declining and identify the factors influencing these changes.